

Visualization on static tensile test for unidirectional CFRP

H. Kusano¹, Y. Aoki², Y. Hirano², T. Hasegawa¹ and Y. Nagao²

1: Analytical & Measuring Instruments Division, Shimadzu Corporation,
3, Kanda-Nishikicho 1-chome, Chiyoda-ku, Tokyo, 101-8448, Japan
hkusano@shimadzu.co.jp

2: Advanced Composite Group, Aerospace Research and Development Directorate,
Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency,
6-13-1 Osawa, Mitaka-shi, Tokyo 181-0015, Japan

SUMMARY

The objective of this study is to visualize the destruction phenomenon of unidirectional CFRP on the solution of destruction mechanisms. The advantages of CFRP are lighter, higher specific stiffness and strength than the metal materials. The tensile fracture mechanism of unidirectional CFRP has not been experimentally made clear because the fracture speed of unidirectional CFRP is quite high.

Keywords: High-speed imaging, High-speed video camera, unidirectional CFRP, static tensile test, fracture, splitting

1. INTRODUCTION

The advantages of CFRP are lighter, higher specific stiffness, and higher specific strength than the metal material. The use of CFRP is expanding into not only the aerospace, the rapid transit railway industry but also the industry on sports, leisure and automobiles and so on. There are some proposed theories to find out the tensile fracture of CFRP by using numerical calculation [1], [2] and numerical simulation [3], [4]. But the tensile fracture mechanism of unidirectional CFRP has not been experimentally made clear because the fracture speed of unidirectional CFRP is quite high.

We selected the Unidirectional CFRP which is simplest on all CFRP. This destruction is known to be very fast generally. It is argued about in the stress and the strain into the material testing. In the static tensile test, we could take some images by high-speed video camera. The time of destruction was 200 microseconds or less, these images were still not enough temporal-resolution. We got a lot of the new results, which was taken by new type High-Speed Video Camera HPV-1[5]. The state of the destruction can be observed in detail from images.

2. EXPERIMENT METHODS AND SPECIMENS

2.1 Material and specimens

The materials used in this study were T800H/3633, T800H/3900-2(TORAY) and IM600/133 (Toho Tenax). These materials have the same characteristics which are reinforced by intermediate modulus, high tensile strength carbon fiber and 180 degrees

centigrade cure-type epoxy resin system (Table 1). A large amount of fundamental data for these materials is available on internet website of JAXA-ACDB [6]. The specifications of specimens are shown as Table 2. These types of the unidirectional CFRP were evaluated, where the length and thickness were different. The evaluation area is drawn by white lines every 10 mm or 5 mm from the center of the specimen to make easy to grasp the conduct of the specimen by the photography. The GFRP (Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastic) tabs are glued to prevent from the stress concentration by grasping tools. Aluminium foils are glued to the specimen to make trigger signals to record.

Table 1 Properties of carbon /epoxy composites used in this study

	T800H/3633	T800H/3900-2	IM600/133
Manufacturer	TORAY (Japan)	TORAY (Japan)	Toho-Tenax (Japan)
Carbon fiber	T800H	T800H	IM600
Matrix	Toughened epoxy #3633	Toughened epoxy #3900-2	Toughened epoxy #133
V _f (%)	55	55	55
E _L (GPa)	156	152	152
v _{LT}	0.34	0.32	0.33

Table 2 Specifications of 4 types specimens

	Specimen-A	Specimen-B	Specimen-C	Specimen-D
Material	T800H/3633	T800H/3900-2	T800H/3900-2	IM600/133
Number of ply (ply)	8	8	4	4
L _f (mm)	254	180	130	160
L _s (mm)	134	60	50	60
W ₁ (mm)	10	10	10	20
T ₁ (mm)	1.13	1.50	0.78	0.58
L _t (mm)	60	60	40	50

2.2 Experiment methods

The materials used in this study were carried out at room temperature using hydraulic testing machine (Instron, 8802) with a load cell of 100kN capacity and mechanical testing machine (Shimadzu, Autograph AG-X) with a load cell of 250kN capacity. The tensile load was applied to the specimen under displacement control with a crosshead speed of 8.3×10^{-6} m/sec (0.5mm/min). High-speed imaging from static tensile test was given by the two high-speed video cameras (shown as Table 3). One of cameras is general purpose and able to record for long time period (TM Research, E2). We record the whole destruction phenomenon by E2. The other (Shimadzu, Hyper Vision HPV-1) is much faster than E2. Maximum recording rate of HPV-1 is up to 1,000,000 frames per second (fps). IS-CCD (In-situ Storage Charge Coupled Device) [7], [8] loaded into HPV-1 can take high-speed photography in 1,000,000 fps. We record the initiation of fracture and the crack growth by HPV-1. We use two metal-halide lamps (Photoron, HVC-SL, 150W) and high power metal halide light source (Moritex, MME-250, 250W). First, test for Specimen-A was carried out in reference to SACMA SRM 4R standards, which inflicted high-speed imaging with E2 and HPV-1. Next, Specimen-B was tested to record the fracture initiation by using HPV-1. Finally, Specimen-C was tested to observe the fracture initiation and the crack growth in more detail. The outlines of experimental system and 3 types of specimen were shown in Figure 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

Figure 1 Overview of unidirectional CFRP specimen

Figure 2 The experimental setup and the grip neighborhood of testing machine

Table 3 Main specification of HPV-1 and E2

	HPV-1	E2
Maximum recording speed (fps)	1,000,000	32,000
Resolution of maximum recording speed (pix)	312 x 260	512 x 32
Frame storage (frame)	100	120,000
Color	Monochrome	Monochrome / Color
Gradations	10 bits	8 bits

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Static tensile tests for three types specimen were carried out, and destructive behaviours of these specimens were recorded by high-speed video cameras at once. Test results and recording conditions were summarized in Table 4.

Table 4 Test results and the recording conditions

Number of test	Type of specimen	Break load [kN]	Strength [MPa]	Recording images	Camera	Flame rate [fps]
1	A	32.8	2890	Figure 3	E2	8,000
				Figure 4	HPV-1	125,000
2	A	35.7	2820	Figure 5	HPV-1	250,000
3	B	36.4	2400	Figure 6	HPV-1	500,000
4	C	20.1	2690	Figure 7	HPV-1	500,000
5	C	21.4	2690	Figure 8	HPV-1	1,000,000
6	D	33.2	2860	Figure 10	HPV-1	500,000

3.1 High-speed imaging results

The high-speed camera observation is performed with 8,000 fps and 125,000 fps in Test-1. Figure 3 shows the series of successive images taken by E2 camera with 8,000 fps. The whole history is grasped by these images and it is possible to understand the specimen broke within 1 millisecond. However, these images are not enough to grasp the fracture initiation and process behaviour. The significant fracture occurred between first and second images.

Figure 3 High-speed image taken by E2 (8,000 fps)

Figure 4 shows the images of 125,000 fps taken by HPV-1. From these images, the time needed for capturing fracture behaviour is measured as only 80 microseconds. The fracture begins from left hand of the specimen in the form of crack like damage, breaking carbon fiber transversely, and which causes a lot of splitting in the longitudinal direction, i.e. fiber direction. The each fragment in splitting specimen shows rippled behaviour before its collapse, which implies that the fracture of specimen induces stress wave propagation in the fiber direction. After specimen collapsed, small fragments are observed in the images.

Figure 4 High-speed imaging taken by HPV-1 (125,000 fps)

3.2 Higher-speed recording results

To record images at higher speed, the reliability of the trigger system is important. Test-2 is same condition of Test-1, and the recording speed was changed to 250,000 fps. The images taken in Test-2 are shown in Figure 5. The aluminium foil trigger follows 250,000 fps in this case. It is found that the crack occurred from the left end of the specimen and went through 10 mm specimen width within 20 microseconds. Therefore, the crack propagation speed is faster than 500m/sec.

Figure 5 Crack growths crossing at right angle with fiber (250,000 fps)

3.3 Improve the capability to capture the fracture initiation

It is important to capture the fracture initiation of the materials. Specimen-A is much bigger than the photographic-coverage. It is impossible to specify a crack initiation point in the present situation. Therefore, we use a short length specimen (Specimen-B). Making a specimen shorter, the observation area can be made smaller in the specimen. We confirm that shorter specimens don't influence a material testing result. When the specimen is too short in the material testing, the stress concentrated on the edge of the specimen, and the specimen is generally broken under the break load. The strength and

behaviour of Test-3 are equivalent to those of Test-1 and Test-2. This result proved that length of Specimen-B doesn't have any influences on the material testing. In Figure 6, the horizontal crack occurred first to be followed by the vertical cracks.

Figure 6 Crack growth and splitting (500,000 fps)

3.4 Effect of the specimen thickness

To examine the effect of specimen thickness on fracture behavior, the number of ply was changed from 8ply to 4ply (Specimen-C) in Test-4. The strength of unidirectional CFRP depends on the number of ply. Generally, strengths are considered to decrease as the thickness increases, and the effect have been widely discussed [9]. In present study, strength of Specimen-C is higher than that of Specimen-B, which is same tendency as reported. The images in Test-4 are shown in Figure 7. We can see that the horizontal crack occurred earlier than the vertical cracks did, which phenomenon is same as Specimen-B. In this case, two cracks occurred. The first crack occurred in the center of specimen which is the early stage of fracture. The other one is the secondary fracture caused by the first crack. The first crack initiated from one of the edges. Fibers at crack tip are broken and the applied load transferred to surrounding fibers. Then, the stresses of intact fibers are influenced by the broken fibers. This condition is generally known as the “local load sharing (LLS)” condition [10]. In the Specimen-C, there are some critical clusters in the vicinity of second crack tip and the LLS condition is affected by those clusters where the local stress concentrated excessively. As for this, a load in the specimen is reallocated by the first crack initiation and the secondary fiber fracture occurs in the part of comparatively low strength. That results in parallel two cracks propagation and contributes to final fracture of specimen. The existing probability of the critical cluster increases as the size or volume of the specimen increases.

Figure 7 Whole specimen of the destruction in 4 ply (500,000 fps)

This is considered to be the main reason for the reduction in the strength as thickness increases. The crack propagation through the width direction is completed within 20 microseconds, and then the speed of crack growth is above 500m/sec. Also, it is possible to suppose that it can be judged from the delay time of the secondary crack occurrence and that it relates to the transmission of the stress wave which occurred to the early stage damage occurrence time. In this case, the fracture sometimes occurred in

the two or more places at one specimen. To specify a fracture part is very important for observation of break-surface. It notes that we should pay attention to the crack growth process when making clear the tensile fracture mechanism of unidirectional CFRP.

3.5 Highest-speed recording for 4ply specimen

The images taken by Test-5 with 1,000,000fps are shown in Figure 8. As same as Test-4 result, the crack grows transversely to the carbon fiber direction. After this crack passes through the width of the specimen, some cracks occur in the direction of carbon fiber. Figure 9 is the schematic view of tracing the crack process shown in Figure 8. We can see this crack went through the specimen width within 10 microseconds. The speed of this growth is about 1000 m/sec by the calculation. It can be diagonally seen. The crack cannot be always observed to grow perpendicularly to the carbon fiber direction because this is the following of the spatial-resolution of crack to the fiber direction or the vertical fiber direction.

Figure 8 Crack growth and splitting (1,000,000 fps)

Figure 9 Picked out only crack from Figure 8

3.6 Introduction examination of Digital Image Correlation method

High-speed imaging is qualitative analysis evaluation. Digital Image Correlation method (DIC) [11] is nominated for technique to convert this into fixed-quantity evaluation. The DIC is application of PIV (Particle Imaging Velocimetry). PIV is the technology that fixed-quantity measures the speed distribution of the flow from the movement of the particle, mixing a particle with flow ground, and assuming a particle following a flow. The DIC can express not only the speed but also the distortion. In this case, we painted in a lot of white points like particles on PIV on the specimen-D surface. Figure 10 shows the specific destruction in comparison with the other

specimens. The other samples began to be broken from the both ends. However, this specimen began to be broken from right and left center. A crack ran below. This crack spread through right and left halfway.

Figure 10 Specific destruction (500,000 fps)

Figure 11 Analysis images by the DIC

We analyzed figure 10 in DIC system (La Vision, Strain Master) [12]. Figure 11 is the analysis result. The displacement of the surface was expressed with an arrow. When the displacements are bigger, the arrows are longer. The arrow was downward first. A crack has begun to progress in right and left. The arrow went up and down and turned over. The directions of arrows are reversed on top of the horizontal cracks. And there were difference to the length of the arrows which were next to right and left. The shearing force was occurred by the difference of the directions and the length. It is thought that the splitting occurs by this shear power. The energy saved to the specimen

by a pulling examination was freed by a crack occurring. When energy was freed, the specimens which lengthened shrink instantly.

In recording at 1,000,000fps, the behavior of the crack growth can be taken by the simple trigger system which wrapped aluminum foil around the specimen. This result says that aluminum foil trigger is very sensitive to the behavior of the fracture. This trigger, enable to get high-speed image up to 1,000,000fps, is sufficiently fast for recording the phenomenon during the tensile test for unidirectional CFRP.

In future study, to grasp the minute part of the fracture in the specimen, we need to take high-speed image by using an optical magnification. It will make clear the phenomenon between the fracture and the splitting in more detail by high magnification. When we use high magnification, we cannot observe enough wide area on the specimen. Because of this, we need to estimate the starting point of the crack and the fracture area in the specimen before the catastrophic final fracture begins. And most of static material testing machine doesn't have an enough output temporal resolution. Therefore, to detect the destruction of the specimen in the material testing machine by the output signal, the signal output of the material testing machine should be much faster than conventional testing machine. We try to improve the testing machine to have higher signal output speed and review the improvement to use as the fracture detection trigger signal at 1,000,000 fps recording.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. Technique to record the discrete micro-damage of unidirectional CFRP at high-speed was established. One of reasons is that there were not any high-speed cameras suitable for the fracture phenomenon of CFRP. Not only the old-generation high-speed video camera but also CMOS high-speed camera doesn't have enough recording speed and enough resolution to record these behaviors. The other hand, framing camera and streak camera can get more high-speed images than HPV-1, but those don't have enough image numbers.
2. Trigger signal to start recording high-speed image was very important, how fracture phenomenon was recorded by high-speed camera. It is necessary that trigger signal grasps phenomenon faithfully. When we didn't get any trigger signal, high-speed imaging was not possible.
3. We clarified that the fiber break expands very fast just before fracture. The crack speed, breaking the carbon fiber, was 1000 m/sec by the calculation based on high-speed image. This was not reported before.
4. In present study, fracture process was recorded successfully. The horizontal crack occurred first and which induce the splitting along the carbon fiber. Then the specimen was broken catastrophically.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Special thanks for Mr. T. Mizuno, MARUBUN Corporation, who introduced DIC in this study.

References

1. H. Suemasu, "Probabilistic aspects of strength of unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites with matrix failure", *Journal of Materials Science* 19, pp.574-584 (1984).
2. S. Leigh Phoenix and Irene J. Beyerlein, "Comprehensive Composite Materials", Volume 1, Sec.1.19, Elsevier Science, pp.559-639 (2000).
3. M. Tanaka, I. Okumura, S. Ochiai, M. Hojo, M. Sato, T. Ishikawa and K. Matsunaga, "Monte Carlo simulation on fracture behaviour of unidirectional fiber reinforced ceramics based on mesomechanics", OS09W0090, ATEM'03, JSME-MMD (2003).
4. M. Tanaka, M. Hojo, S. Ochiai, Y. Hirosawa, K. Fujita and Y. Sawada, "Effect of uniformity of fiber arrangement on tensile fracture behavior of unidirectional model composites", in *Proceedings of 16th International Conference on Composite Materials* (2007).
5. Y. Kondo, H. Maruno, H. Tominaga, H. Soya and T.G. Etoh, "An Ultra High-Speed Video Camera and Its Applications", in *Proceedings of 25th ICHSPP* (2002).
6. T.G. Etoh, K. Takehara, T. Okinaka, Y. Takano, A. Ruckelshausen, D. Poggemann, "Development of high-speed video cameras", *Proceedings 24th International Congress on High-Speed Photography and Photonics*, SPIE Vol.4183, pp.36-47 (2001)
7. T.G. Etoh et al., "A CCD image sensor of 1M frames/s for continuous image capturing of 103 frames", *Digest of Technical Papers, ISSCC02*, pp. 46-47 (2002).
8. M.R. Wisnom, Size effects in the testing of fiber-composite materials, *Compos Science and Technology* Vol. 59, pp.1937-57 (1999).
9. T. Okabe and N. Takeda, Size effect on tensile strength of unidirectional CFRP composites—experiment and simulation, *Composites Science and Technology* Vol. 62, pp. 2053-2064, (2002).
10. Web page, Advanced Composites Database System: JAXA-ACDB, Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency, <http://www.jaxa-acdb.com/>
11. Web page, Techniques of Digital Image Correlation, La Vision, http://www.lavision.de/techniques/digital_image_correlation.php
12. Web page, Product of Strain Master, La Vision, <http://www.lavision.de/products/strainmaster.php>